

yellowing virus. This is the first report of the occurrence of this disease in the tropics. ■

Transmission of rice tungro virus from stubbles of different rice varieties 30, 60, 90, and 120 days after harvest. West Bengal, India, 1978.

Variety	Transmission (%) in seedlings			
	30 days	60 days	90 days	120 days
Ratna	10	0	0	0
Pankaj	10	5	0	0
Cauvery	0	0	0	0
IET1441	0	0	0	0
IR579	20	10	0	0
IET2295	0	0	0	0
IET2914	30	20	10	0
Jaya	20	10	0	0
IR8	10	0	0	0
Laghu	20	10	0	0
Kathamuk	20	10	0	0
Rajmalati	20	5	0	0
Kalamkathi	10	0	0	0
Lakhansail	20	10	0	0
Sachimohan	20	10	0	0
Jhulur	10	0	0	0
Dhushri	20	10	0	0
Dudshar	10	0	0	0
Ashanlaya	20	10	0	0
Madhumalati	20	10	0	0

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Further studies on the potential of rice stubble for spreading tungro in West Bengal, India

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A previous study on the potential of rice stubble in spreading tungro in West Bengal confirmed that infected stubbles of TN1 plants can act as a virus source and maintain the virus for 75 days. The same procedure was used to test the infected stubbles of high yielding and local varieties for efficiency in transmitting virus.

Of the nine high yielding varieties (Ratna, Pankaj, Cauvery, IET1441, IR579, IET2295, IET2914, Jaya, and IR8) and 11 local varieties (Laghu, Kathamuk, Rajmalati, Kalamkathi, Lakhansail, Sachimohan, Jhulur, Dhushri, Dudshar, Ashanlaya, and Madhumalati) tested (see table), Ratna and IR8

retained the virus in the stubbles for only 30 days; Pankaj, IR579, and Jaya for 60 days; and IET2914 for 90 days. The stubbles of Cauvery, IET1441, and IET2295 carried no virus.

Of the local varieties tested, Kalamkathi and Dudshar carried the virus in the stubbles for only 30 days;

the stubbles of Laghu, Rajmalati, Lakhansail, Sachimohan, Ashanlaya, and Madhumalati retained the virus for 60 days; and those of Kathamuk and Dhushri for 90 days (see table). The research was funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi. ■

Effect of transplanting date and seedling age at transplanting on spread of tungro

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Experiments were conducted at the plant virus experimental field to determine the effect of transplanting date and of

seedling age at transplanting on the spread of tungro virus disease in a rice crop during 1978 kharif. The Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi, funded the research.

In the first experiment 25-day-old TN1 seedlings were transplanted at 5-day intervals in 3-m² replicated plots provided with uniform inoculum for tungro virus (1 infected plant/plot). The

number of plants with tungro symptoms was recorded at 3- to 6-day intervals until the end of September.

Transplanting date had pronounced effects on the spread of tungro (see table). The spread of the disease increased when the transplanting date gradually shifted from mid-July to the first week of August, when spread became maximum. With subsequent shifts of

Effect of transplanting date and age at transplanting of TN1 seedlings on the spread of rice tungro virus (RTV) disease during 1978 kharif (Jul–Nov) and the corresponding vector population in the field, West Bengal, India.

Date of observation	LH ^a (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)	LH (no.)		RTV infection (%)			
	A	N		A	N		A	N		A	N		A	N				
	Effect of transplanting date of 25-day-old TN1 seedlings																	
	16 Jul			21 Jul			26 Jul			1 Aug			6 Aug			11 Aug		
28 Jul	0	0	—	0	0	—	0	0	—									
2 Aug	1	0	—	1	0	—	2	0	—	0	0	—						
7 Aug	0	2	—	4	2	—	3	9	—	3	10	—	3	5	—			
12 Aug	1	1	—	1	37	—	3	70	—	2	38	—	3	82	—	4	11	—
17 Aug	1	0	—	0	15	—	0	20	—	0	40	—	0	43	—	2	3	—

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